

ISic1116

I.Sicily inscription 1116

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance

Probably NW Sicily: Mozia, Erice (?)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8796

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Κλεαγόρας Μασσαλιώτης Ἀφροδίτη
2. ἀνέθηκε τράπηζαν

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491444

EDR 140612

EDCS 39102273

PHI 140599

PHI 175739

Bibliography

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